

STUDIES IN VAT DYES. PART V. THE ACYL DERIVATIVES OF MONO- AND DI-AMINOANTHRAQUINONES USING LONG-CHAIN FATTY ACIDS

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Lauryl, palmyl and stearyl derivatives of 1-amino-, 2-amino-, 1:4-diamino-, 1:5-diamino- and 2:6-diaminoanthraquinones have been prepared. These amidanthraquinones are useless as vat dyes owing to their inability to vat, but are soluble in vegetable oils.

Among the anthraquinone vat dyes, the acylamidoanthraquinones are notable for their simplicity of structure and the method of preparation. The aminoanthraquinones are capable of vattine, but the alkali salts of the "leuco" compounds have no affinity for cotton. Deinet (*J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1914, 30, 29) observed that benzylation of 1-aminoanthraquinones had the remarkable effect of transforming them into vat dyes, with adequate affinity for practical dyeing. It is an important fact that one or more of the acylamido groups must be in the α -position of the anthraquinone nucleus. While α -benzamideanthraquinone is a yellow vat dye (Algol yellow WG; CI, 1126; Bayer & Co., E.P. 270209; U.S.P. 957041; G.P. 216772, 225232), the β -isomer is devoid of any dyeing property. The simple monobasic, as well as dibasic, aliphatic and aromatic acids have been used for acylation, but long-chain fatty acids have not been used. We therefore thought of preparing this type of compounds by condensing acid chlorides of long-chain fatty acids, viz. lauric acid, palmitic acid and stearic acid, with various mono- and di-aminoanthraquinones, viz. 1-aminoanthraquinone, 2-aminoanthraquinone, 1:4-diaminoanthraquinone, 1:5-diaminoanthraquinone and 2:6-diaminoanthraquinone. The acylation has been carried out by condensing previously prepared acid chlorides with the various aminoanthraquinones in presence of dry nitrobenzene.

In the case of diaminoanthraquinones, one acyl group reacted with only one amino group. The structures of these compounds have been proved by preparing their acetyl derivatives, whereby their free amino groups reacted with acetic anhydride, forming the acetylamido-acylamidoanthraquinones. The compounds so formed are highly coloured, varying from golden yellow to brick-red, but owing to their inability to vat, they are useless as vat dyes. However, they are soluble in vegetable oils.

EXPERIMENTAL

The acid chlorides were prepared using thionyl chloride at 60°-70° (Beilstein, Vol. 2, pp. 363, 374, 384).

1-Stearylamidoanthraquinone was prepared by condensing 1-aminoanthraquinone (10 g.) with stearyl chloride (13.1 g.) in presence of nitrobenzene (80 c.c.), using an air condenser. It crystallised from chlorobenzene as golden yellow shining needles, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 2.6. $C_{32}H_{48}O_2N$ requires N, 2.86 per cent).

All other compounds of the series, prepared in a similar manner, are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound.	S = Stearyl-amido- Form and solvent.	P = Palmityl-amido- Formula.	M.P.	L = Lauryl-amido- % Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
2-S-A.	Lemon-yellow plates from toluene.	$C_{23}H_{43}O_3N$	184°	2.77	2.86
4-Amino-1-S-A.	Dark violet needles from nitrobenzene.	$C_{27}H_{44}O_3N_2$	112°	5.30	5.55
4-Acetyl-amido-1-S-A.	Reddish violet shining amorphous powder from acetic acid.	$C_{31}H_{46}O_4N_2$	99°	5.00	5.12
5-Amino-1-S-A.	Bright golden yellow needles from benzene.	$C_{32}H_{44}O_3N_2$	120°	5.40	5.55
5-Acetyl-amido-1-S-A.	Orange amorphous powder from acetic acid.	$C_{31}H_{46}O_4N_2$	143°	5.20	5.12
6-Amino-2-S-A.	Brownish amorphous powder from nitrobenzene.	$C_{32}H_{44}O_3N_2$	272°	5.60	5.55
6-Acetyl-amido-2-S-A.	Blackish brown powder from acetic acid.	$C_{31}H_{46}O_4N_2$	72°	5.17	5.12
1-P-A.	Bright golden yellow needles from aviation spirit (b.p. 80-120°).	$C_{32}H_{44}O_3N$	129°	2.57	3.00
2-P-A.	Lemon-yellow flakes from xylene.	$C_{32}H_{44}O_3N$	182°	2.78	3.00
4-Amino-1-P-A.	Deep violet needles from toluene.	$C_{30}H_{40}O_3N_2$	115°	5.76	5.88
4-Acetyl-amido-1-P-A.	Dark violet powder from acetic acid.	$C_{32}H_{42}O_4N_2$	122°	5.47	5.40
5-Amino-1-P-A.	Shining golden yellow needles from aviation spirit (b.p. 80-120°).	$C_{30}H_{40}O_3N_2$	123°	5.69	5.88
5-Acetyl-amido-1-P-A.	Yellowish orange crystals from acetic acid.	$C_{32}H_{42}O_4N_2$	168°	5.34	5.40
6-Amino-2-P-A.	Brownish amorphous powder from nitrobenzene.	$C_{30}H_{40}O_3N_2$	280°	6.00	5.88
6-Acetyl-amido-2-P-A.	Dark brown powder from acetic acid.	$C_{31}H_{42}O_4N_2$	292°	5.30	5.40
1-L-A.	Golden yellow needles from aviation spirit (b.p. 80-120°).	$C_{26}H_{31}O_3N$	128°	3.30	3.45
2-L-A.	Yellow needles from alcohol.	$C_{26}H_{31}O_3N$	188°	3.50	3.45
4-Amino-1-L-A.	Amorphous powder from methyl alcohol.	$C_{26}H_{31}O_2N_2$	114°	6.72	6.60
4-Acetyl-amido-1-L-A.	Violet powder from acetic acid.	$C_{28}H_{34}O_4N_2$	130°	5.82	6.00
5-Amino-1-L-A.	Microscopic golden yellow needles from aviation spirit (b.p. 80-120°).	$C_{26}H_{31}O_3N_2$	150°	6.50	6.60
5-Acetyl-amido-1-L-A.	Orange microscopic needles from acetic acid.	$C_{28}H_{34}O_4N_2$	156°	6.10	6.00
6-Amino-2-L-A.	Brownish amorphous powder from aniline.	$C_{26}H_{31}O_3N_2$	287°	6.55	6.60
6-Acetyl-amido-2-L-A.	Dark brown amorphous powder from acetic acid.	$C_{28}H_{34}O_4N_2$	286°	6.20	6.00

The authors take this opportunity in expressing their grateful thanks to the Governing Body of the Ahmedabad Education Society for the provision of research facilities.